

Physico-Chemical Studies on Cu (II)-2, 4 Dihydroxybenzoic Acid Chelate

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Gupta and Soni¹ investigated a green water soluble complex between Cu⁺² and 2 : 4 dihydroxybenzoic acid in acidic medium. This study has further been extended for the determination of instability constants at different ionic strengths and at various temperatures. The instability constants of the complex (K_{in}) have been calculated at various ionic strengths as mentioned in our earlier paper² and are reported in Table I.

TABLE I

Effect of ionic strength on the instability constant of the complex between Cu⁺² ion and 2 : 4 dihydroxybenzoic acid in acidic medium.

$\lambda = 390 \text{ m}\mu$; $pH = 5.5$; $Temp. = 30^\circ \pm 0.1$

Ionic strength	Instability constant
0.01	1.88×10^{-3}
0.02	2.05×10^{-3}
0.03	2.16×10^{-3}
0.05	2.31×10^{-3}
0.08	2.57×10^{-3}
0.10	2.81×10^{-3}
0.15	3.04×10^{-3}
0.20	3.20×10^{-3}

The instability constants of the complex at a constant ionic strength have also been determined at different temperatures. The results are given in Table II. The plot of log K against the reciprocal of absolute temperature is practically a straight line. Thus the heat

1. S. L. Gupta and R. N. Soni, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **43**, 331.

2. S. L. Gupta and R. N. Soni, *ibid.*, 1966, **43**, 311.

TABLE II

Instability constant of the complex at different temperatures.

Ionic strength = 0.01; $\lambda = 390 \text{ m}\mu$; $p\text{H} = 5.5$

Temp. °K	Instability constant
283.16	1.94×10^{-3}
293.16	1.88×10^{-3}
303.16	1.70×10^{-3}
313.16	1.58×10^{-3}
323.16	1.47×10^{-3}
333.16	1.36×10^{-3}

of dissociation can be assumed to be practically constant, and ΔH may be calculated from the equation $d \log K/dT = \Delta H/2.303 RT^2$. ΔH is found to be -1.5 k.cal/mole . The value of ΔS has been calculated as 17.7 e.u.

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